

Educating Students for Creativity and Entrepreneurship Skills Development in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

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Abstract

The main trust of this study was to investigate how we can educate students for creativity and entrepreneurship skills development in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study which adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised of 8, 694 teachers in the 274 public secondary schools in Rivers State. A sample of 870 teachers (470 male and 400 female) was drawn through stratified random sampling technique. Data were collected with a self-structured questionnaire entitled: “Educating Students for Creativity and Entrepreneurship Skills Development Questionnaire (ESCESDQ)”. The instrument which was well validated by experienced scholars in the Department of Educational Management, Rivers State University, had a reliability index of 0.86 established through Cronbach Alpha Method. Mean, Standard Deviation and rank order were used to analyse the research questions while z-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results of the study revealed that ways we can educate students for creativity include among others: setting up learning activities that allow students to explore their creativity; encouraging creative thinking through the use of provocative questions; and through giving open ended assignments. While, ways we can educate students for entrepreneurship skills develop include among others: use of activity- based teaching method; through school-industry linkage and by organizing internship programmes for students. Based on the findings, conclusion was drawn and the following recommendations among others were made: government should on regular basis organize seminars/workshops to refresh teachers pedagogical skills; and teachers should motivate their students to acquire creative and entrepreneurship skills because they are critical to individual and national development.

Keywords: *Education, Students, Creative Skills, Entrepreneurship Skills and Secondary Education.*

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Introduction

Education is said to be the best gift any child or individual can receive from his/her parents and the government. It is through education that character, skills and values are impacted into human beings. The basic reason for the huge investment in education by government and individuals is to equip individuals with the skills, competences and knowledge that will enable them to cope within the dynamic world. Educating the citizens and equipping them with the relevant skills will also

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enable them to meaningfully contribute to the sustainable development and transformation of their societies. Hence, it is believed that education is the best predictor of skills acquisition and the greatest tool for individual and national development.

According to FRN (2014:11) one of the objectives of secondary education is to raise a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feelings of others, respect the dignity of labour, appreciate those values specified under the broad national goals and live as good citizens. These can only be achieved with a population that possess the relevant skills and creativity required for a nation's socio-economic development. Education at the secondary school level stands as a critical factor in the development of any nation because, the knowledge and skills acquired at this level of education, to a large extent determine the quality of manpower supply in the country especially at the middle level, the labour market outcomes and other outcomes in the society.

Educating students for creativity and skills development is essential for the attainment of sustainable national development because a higher creative and skillful level of education generally creates more favourable employment prospects and consequently opens up the possibility for better living conditions for the youths. Creativity is associated with critical thinking. It has to do with the disposition of the mind such as imagination, visualization, thinking styles and logical reasoning. It equally has to do with personality traits such as originality, independence, objectivity, risk taking, energy, curiosity, inquisitiveness, open mindedness, readiness to try new ways to doing things and consideration of alternatives, insightfulness and persistence (Ajaezu, 2017: 28).

Creativity in every sense is one of the fundamentals of development. According to Franken in Umar (2017), creativity is the tendency to generate or recognize ideas, alternatives or possibilities that may be useful in solving problems, communicating with others and entertaining ourselves and others. Creativity is the act of turning new and imaginative ideas into reality (Linda, 2010). For something to be creative, it must involve the process of thinking and producing something new.

Entrepreneurship skills are very relevant to secondary school students and graduates. As adolescents, they need these skills in managing challenges of life. Entrepreneurship skills will help beneficiaries to become self reliant. Educating students for creativity and entrepreneurship skills development is aimed at sustaining economic growth by reducing poverty and improving productivity. Acquisition of entrepreneurship skills will enable individuals to participate in a modern economy and society. Educating students for creativity and entrepreneurship skills development is therefore an instrument for developing individuals socially, mentally, physically, emotionally, morally and psychologically. A combination of creative and entrepreneurship skills will help people to adequately bring together innovation ideas in utilizing money and other resources to meet an identified need, create wealth and contribute meaningfully to sustainable national development.

It is therefore imperative for us to find out how we can educate individuals for creativity and entrepreneurship skills development bearing in mind the impact these skills will have on the individuals who possess them. It is on this note that the researcher felt bothered and decided to investigate how we can educate students for creativity and entrepreneurship development in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

In recent times, there has been a public outcry on the issue of skills acquisition by students in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Parents, employers of labour and other stakeholders in the education sector have expressed their dissatisfaction over the poor standard of skills acquisition of secondary school students in the state. Most of the secondary school graduates lack creative and entrepreneurship skills which are vital for securing employment and becoming self employed.

Hence, they are handicapped, unemployed and helpless after their graduation. This situation promotes hunger, poverty and underdevelopment of our nation.

There is the need to change this narrative by ensuring that students are educated for creativity and entrepreneurship skills development. This will enhance their preparation for useful living within the society as well as sustainable national development. Therefore, the problem of this study is to find out how we can educate students for creativity and entrepreneurship skills development in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate how we can educate students for creativity and entrepreneurship skills development in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

1. examine how we can educate students for creativity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. determine how we can educate students for entrepreneurship skills development in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in this study:

1. How can we educate students for creativity in public secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. How can we educate students for entrepreneurship skills development in public secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the ways we can educate students for creativity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the ways we can educate students for entrepreneurship skills development in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the human capital theory (HCT) propounded by Adams Smith in 1776 and has been expanded by scholars like Schultz in 1971, Sakamota and Powers in 1995, Psacharopoulos and Woodhall in 1997. The theory rests on the assumption that formal education is highly instrumental and very important in the improvement of the productive capacity of individuals. The human capital theorists argued that an educated population is a productive population. They laid emphasis on how education enhances the productivity and efficiency of individuals and workers through skills development. To them, education and training equip their beneficiaries with greater level of knowledge, skills and other competencies which help them to achieve greater performance outcomes than those who didn't acquire it. Educating students for creativity and entrepreneurship skills development is a major component of human capital development and pathway to sustainable national development. It is therefore necessary for our

educational system to ensure that they impact all the relevant skills to their students and empower them for useful living and meaningful contribution to the development of their society.

Conceptual Literature Review

Concept of Education

Education is the process of training and instruction which is designed to teach knowledge and develop skills. It is the process of equipping individuals to become useful members of the society. Education according to Ogonor and Igenegbai (2019) is the acquisition of knowledge, attitudes, values and skills to enable individuals become useful members of the society. Ilueme and Ebirim (2016) see education as the approved process in a conducive environment of actual teaching by a determined and qualified teacher to a prepared learner willingly learning with the unanimous aim of achieving predetermined objectives which have positive value to the society. In the view of Parankimalil (2012), education is a systematic process through which an individual acquires knowledge, experience, skill and sound attitude, to make him civilized, refined, cultured and educated.

Educating people for creativity and entrepreneurship skills development is the process of impacting or helping individuals acquire creative thinking or behaviour and entrepreneurship skills through teaching and learning. Creativity according to Nziadam (2020) is associated with the process of producing ideas that are novel, useful and meet the need of the people. Divergent thinking is an integral part of creativity (Onu, 2007). Factors involved in divergent thinking include sensitivity to problems, fluency, novel ideas, flexibility, ability to synthesize, recognize, or redefine complexities and evaluation. According to Akinboye (2003) creativity is the most fundamental of all human resources and skills because when one learns to think creatively, the quality of his future is enhanced. Creativity is the process of challenging accepted ideas and ways of doing things in order to find new solutions or concepts.

Creativity is viewed as a process of solving problems and a means of giving hope to emerging intellectuals. Hence, it is important to educate individuals for creativity in order to reason outside the old ideas, concepts and perceptions, and provide a means of doing things differently. Impacting creative skills to students therefore, demands that schools should create a conducive environment that encourages creative performance. There is no single recipe or method to inculcating creative skills into the students. Rather, there are some steps or teaching approaches that lend themselves more readily to creating a creative context. A teaching method according Nziadam (2020) becomes creative as it is used by the teacher in such a manner that it brings forth creative thinking and activity within the learners.

To foster creative skills in students, the following steps according to <https://www.edutopia.org> could be taken:

- Setup learning activities that allow students to explore their creativity in relevant, interesting and worthwhile ways.
- Value creativity, celebrate and reward it.
- Teach students the other skills they need to be creative
- Remove constraints for creativity and give the students space and a framework in which they can be creative.

Developing creative skills in students will involve creating a flexible classroom layout with a library, giving open ended assignments and using alternatives to rote learning; exercising patience, working in group, providing feedback, taking advantage of curiosity, exercising your own creativity and experimenting with new activities (Drexel.edu/soc/res).

In a creative learning environment, the teacher is seen as a resource provider and director of divergent learning activities. The teacher controls the classroom environment where students spend so much time on daily basis. They serve as role models, who stimulate and sustain students creative thinking process. Torrance and Myers (2007) threw more light on educational methods that could facilitate creative learning and divergent thinking. They suggested the following strategies.

- Present ambiguous, uncertainties and incompleteness.
- Heighten anticipation, and expectation for what is to come
- Look at the same thing from a variety of psychological, sociological, cultural, physical or emotional point of view.
- Ask provocative question.
- Encourage students to step out of their comfort zone of the known and familiar.
- Explore missing elements and new possibilities
- Use surprises
- Work to make events and places concrete and visual.
- Experiment and test ideas.
- Encourage hypothesis
- Transform and rearrange information

Entrepreneurship education is a form of education that is designed to provide knowledge, skills, attitude and motivation to students for entrepreneurial success in any setting. It equips the students with the ability to seek investment opportunities. According to UNESCO (2008) entrepreneurship education is made up of all kinds of experiences that give students the ability and vision of how to access and transform opportunities of different kinds. Entrepreneurship education is designed to equip students with entrepreneurship skills. According to Arome and Aminu in Joshua (2019), entrepreneurship education seeks to achieve the following objectives:

- Offer functional education to the youths that will enable them to be self-employed and self-reliant.
- Provide the youth graduates with adequate training that will enable them to be creative and innovative in identifying novel business opportunities.
- Serve as catalyst for economic growth and development.
- Reduce high rate of poverty.
- Reduce rural-urban migration
- Provide the youths with adequate training and support that will enable them to establish a career in small and medium size businesses.

Entrepreneurship education develops entrepreneurship skills in the students and it offers quick solution to problems of unemployment and poverty among others. According to Shamsuddin, Arome And Aminu (2018), acquisition of entrepreneurial skills through entrepreneurship education is most desirable at this time in Nigeria, when poverty level and unemployment rate is very high. Moreover, most of the programmes introduced by federal government to reduce poverty and unemployment appeared to have either failed or were not fulfilling the expected results because school graduates lacked the practical skills which can be acquired through entrepreneurship

education. the big question in this case is what are these entrepreneurship skills, and how can we educate students for entrepreneurship skills development?

Entrepreneurship skills are the various skills sets such as leadership skills, business management skills, time management skills, creative thinking and problem-solving skills. These skills are very important in enhancing innovation, business growth and competitiveness (<https://www.smilefoundation>) entrepreneurship skills could be divided into soft skills and hard skills (<https://unctad.org>topic>3-skill>). The soft skills include persistence, networking and self-confidence, while the enabling or hard skills include start-up knowledge, business planning, financial literacy and managerial skills. Effective entrepreneurship education policies and programmes focus on developing these entrepreneurship competences and skills.

According to Wilfred-Bonse and Sam-Ngwu (2014) one of the best methods of developing entrepreneurship skills in students is through school-industry linkage. It is the process through which the school gains and gives assistance to the industry and the industry in turn exposes students to real and practical job experience. Akani (2011) suggested the following strategies for the development of entrepreneurship skills in students:

- Organize internship programmes for students. .
- Organize seminars and workshops for students.
- Provide practical counselling on entrepreneurship and skill acquisition for students.
- Helping students to have access to soft loans to enable them start their various businesses.
- Rewarding students that perform well in entrepreneurship and skills acquisition activities.

Yusuf (2011) in his own study revealed the following as methods of developing entrepreneurship skills in students:

- Activity based method
- Learner/child centered method
- Problem solving method.
- Excursion method
- Demonstration method
- Science- technology- society method.

These approaches, if adequately utilized and combined will help to inculcate most of the entrepreneurship skills to our students. Ivowi (2011) advised teachers to maximize the use of these methods in their classrooms. Teachers are encouraged to motivate their students and promote the development of these skills in students.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised of 8,694 teachers in the 274 public secondary schools in Rivers State. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. A sample of 870 teachers (470 male and 400 female) was drawn through stratified random sampling technique. Data were collected using a self-structured questionnaire entitled: “Educating Students for Creativity and Entrepreneurship skills Development Questionnaire (ESCESDQ).” The questionnaire was well validated by experienced researchers in the Department of Educational Management, Rivers State University. A reliability

test was carried out using Cronbach Alpha method and a reliability index of 0.86 was obtained. The research questions were answered using mean, standard deviation and rank order analysis while, z-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: How can we educate students for creativity in public secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 1. Analysis of Mean Scores, Standard Deviation and Rank Order of Male and Female Teachers' Responses on Ways We Can Educate Students for Creativity in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/N	Items	Male Teachers N= 470		Female Teacher N = 400		Mean Set	Rank Order	Decisions
1.	Setting up learning activities that allow students to explore their creativity in relevant interesting and worthwhile manner.	2.93	0.89	2.90	0.88	2.92	4 th	Agree
2.	By encouraging creative thinking through the use of provocative questions.	2.88	0.87	2.84	0.90	2.86	6 th	Agree
3.	By giving open ended assignments	3.00	0.83	2.96	0.86	2.98	3 rd	Agree
4.	Encourage hypothesis and testing of new ideas.	2.98	0.85	3.00	0.84	2.99	2 nd	Agree
5.	Encourage students to look at the something from different perspectives.	3.02	0.81	3.04	0.80	3.03	1 st	Agree
6.	Discouraging rote learning by using other alternatives to it.	2.96	0.86	2.88	0.89	2.92	4 th	Agree
7.	By valuing creativity, celebrating and rewarding it.	2.86	0.91	2.82	0.93	2.84	7 th	Agree
8.	By encouraging students to imitate or copy from others.	2.38	0.95	2.34	0.97	2.36	8 th	Disagree
	Aggregate mean and standard deviation	2.88	0.87	2.85	0.88			

Note: Criterion mean= 2.50

Results in table 1 show that all the items (1 to 7) have mean scores that are greater than the criterion mean except item 8. Items 1 to 7 were accepted as the ways we can educate students for creativity in public secondary schools in Rivers State while item 8 was rejected. In terms of rank order, item 5 ranked 1st while item 8 ranked 8th position. The aggregate mean score of 2.88 and 2.85 for male and female teachers are very close, indicating that the respondents shared a common opinion on ways we can educate students for creativity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Therefore, the ways we can educate students for creativity in public secondary schools in Rivers State include: setting up learning activities that allow students to explore their creativity in relevant, interesting and worthwhile manner; by encouraging creative thinking through the use of provocative questions; through giving open ended assignments; encouraging hypothesis and testing

of new ideas; encouraging students to look at the same thing from different perspectives; by discouraging rote learning; and by valuing creativity, celebrating and rewarding it.

Research Question 2: How can we educate students for entrepreneurship skills development in public secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 2. Analysis of Mean Scores, Standard Deviation and Rank Order of Male and Female Teachers' Responses on Ways of Educating Students for Entrepreneurship Skills Development in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/N	Items	Male Teachers N= 470		Female Teacher N = 400		Mean Set	Rank Order	Decisions
1.	By using activity-based method of teaching.	3.04	0.74	3.06	0.74	3.05	1 st	Agree
2.	By adopting problem-solving method of teaching.	3.00	0.77	2.92	0.83	2.96	5 th	Agree
3.	By using demonstration method.	3.02	0.75	3.04	0.76	3.03	2 nd	Agree
4.	By employing learner/child centered method of teaching.	2.96	0.80	2.90	0.85	2.93	7 th	Agree
5.	By organizing seminars, workshops and exhibitions.	2.98	0.79	2.94	0.81	2.96	5 th	Agree
6.	By organizing internship programmes for students.	3.08	0.72	2.98	0.79	3.03	2 nd	Agree
7.	Through school-industry collaboration/linkage	3.06	0.73	3.00	0.77	3.03	2 nd	Agree
8.	By providing practical counselling on entrepreneurship and skills acquisition to students.	2.92	0.82	2.88	0.86	2.90	8 th	Agree
9.	By encouraging students to recite passages of hand.	2.42	0.84	2.34	0.90	2.38	9 th	Disagree
10.	By using lecture method of teaching.	2.36	0.86	2.38	0.88	2.37	10 th	
	Aggregate mean and standard deviation	2.88	0.78	2.84	0.82			

Note: Criterion mean = 2.50

Data in table 2 reveal that items 1 to 8 have mean scores that are greater than the criterion mean and were agreed on by the respondents as ways we can educate students for entrepreneurship skills development. Items 9 and 10 have mean scores that are less than the criterion mean and they were rejected as ways we can educate students for entrepreneurship skills development in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Item 1 ranked 1st in the rank order while item 10 ranked last.

The aggregate mean of 2.88 and 2.84 for male and female respondents appear to be very close, indicating that the respondents unanimously agreed on the items as ways we can educate students for entrepreneurship skills development in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Therefore, ways we can educate students for entrepreneurship skills development include: using activity-based teaching method; adopting problem solving method; using demonstration method; employing learner/child centred method; organizing seminars, workshops and exhibitions; organizing internship programmes for students; school-industry linkage; and by providing practical counselling on entrepreneurship and skills acquisition to students.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the ways we can educate students for creativity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 3. Z-Test of Difference between the Mean Scores of Male and Female Teachers on Ways We Can Educate Students for Creativity in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of sign.	Decision
Male Teachers	470	2.88	0.84	868	0.682	± 1.960	0.05	Ho1 Not Significant
Female Teachers	400	2.85	0.88					

Table 3 shows that the mean scores of male and female teachers stood at 2.88 and 2.85 respectively. At 868 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance, the calculated z-score of 0.682 is by far less than the z-critical or table value of ± 1.960 . Based on this, the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis and therefore affirms that, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the ways we can educate students for creativity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the ways we can educate students for entrepreneurship skills development in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4. Z-Test of Difference between the Mean Scores of Male and Female Teachers on Way We Can Educate Students for Entrepreneurship Skills Development in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of sign.	Decision
Male Teachers	470	2.88	0.78	868	0.496	± 1.960	0.05	Ho2 Not Significant
Female Teachers	400	2.84	0.82					

Table 4 indicates that the mean scores of male and female teachers stood at 2.88 and 2.84 respectively. At 868 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance, the calculated z-score of 0.496 is by far less than the z-critical or table value of ± 1.960 . Based on this, the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis and therefore affirms that, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on ways we can educate students for entrepreneurship skills development in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

The results of the study showed that, the ways we can educate students for creativity in the study area include: setting up learning activities that allow students explore their creativity in relevant, interesting and worthwhile manner; by encouraging creative thinking; by giving open ended questions/assignments; by encouraging hypothesis and testing of new ideas; by encouraging students to look at the same thing from different perspectives; by discouraging rote learning; and by valuing creativity, celebrating and rewarding it. Creative skill is one of the most important skills

every individual requires for survival in life. It is highly valued by employers of labour as an asset needed in every industry. Education is therefore expected to enhance the creative capacity of the students. Teachers should employ different pedagogical approaches in the classroom to reach out to the learning needs of every student. They should create a flexible classroom layout where every student has the freedom of exercising and expressing himself or herself and exploring his/her creativity.

The above findings are in agreement with Nziadam (2020); Torrance and Myers (2007); and Akinboye (2003), who in their different studies pointed out the importance of the development of creative skills in students and the various approaches teachers can adopt to achieve this. The use of open ended questions/assignments will provoke the thinking faculty of the students, thus encouraging critical thinking and divergent reasoning. Open ended assignments and thought provoking questions will lead students to approach issues from different ways. This will also help to discourage rote learning, memorization and doing the same thing same way every time.

Creativity is associated with being innovative and exploring new ideas. In this manner, teachers should encourage students to formulate hypothesis and test them, encourage imagination and out of box thinking. They should make the students not to feel embarrassed and disappointed for taking chances but rather feel comfortable trying new things and making mistakes in the learning process.

Teachers and students should value creativity and handwork. Teachers should celebrate and reward students who are creative as a way of encouragement to others. They should endeavor to remove all hindrances to creativity and give the students space and a framework in which they can be creative.

The study also revealed that entrepreneurship skills can be developed through: the use of activity based teaching method; problem solving method; demonstration method; employing child/learner centred method; by organizing seminars/ workshops; internship for students; through school-industry linkage; and through the provision of practical counselling on entrepreneurship and skills acquisition to students. These findings agree with Wilfred-Bonse and Sam- Ngwu (2014). Akani (2011) and Yusuf (2011). Educating students for entrepreneurship skills development requires teaching them through practical activities, demonstrations, experiments and learner-centred approaches. These methods require active participation of the students and observation of what is going on in the class. Through these activity- based methods, they acquire some skills and utilize such skills in solving some problems on their own.

The organization of seminar/workshops will also expose students to skills acquisition opportunities. They will be taught so many things that will enhance their skills set. Schools should organize seminars/workshops from time to time where resource persons are brought from outside to teach the students. Taking the students out on excursions in places of interest to practically observe things for themselves will equally help to foster entrepreneurship skills in them. The school can partner with industries around them for internship programmes for the students. The students through these arrangements will learn a lot from the different industries.

One of the most important steps in the process of educating students for entrepreneurship skills development is the ability to change their mindset from that of looking for paid or white-collar job to that of becoming self employed and self reliant after their graduation. It therefore behoves on the school management to ensure that practical counselling on entrepreneurship and skills acquisition is provided to the students regularly. This will enable them to understand the importance of entrepreneurship skills acquisition.

Conclusion

Educating students for creativity and entrepreneurship skills development is very necessary at this point in our educational system for individual and national development. As a critical factor in our development process, a lot of emphasis should be paid to it and stakeholders in secondary education should support every effort directed towards educating students for creativity and entrepreneurship skills development. Teachers should be well trained, conversant with and willingly utilize pedagogical approaches that promote creative skills and entrepreneurship skills development in their students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should ensure that only trained and qualified teachers are employed to teach in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. On regular basis, government should organize seminars/workshops for teachers to refresh their pedagogical skills and ways of educating students for creativity and entrepreneurship skills development.
3. There should be adequate provision of infrastructure and instructional materials in public secondary schools in Rivers State in order to enhance the education of students for creativity and entrepreneurship skills development.
4. Teachers should motivate and encourage their students to acquire creative and entrepreneurship skills because they are critical to individual and national development.

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